

INVERSE ANALYSIS FOR COMPOSITE SINGLE-LAP ADHESIVELY BONDED JOINT

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Motivation and Key Issues

- Bonded process and service environment may have effects on the mechanical properties of the interface
- Inspect the interfacial properties to analyze the strain distribution accurately

Inverse Approach

SLJ FE model

Interface parameter	Optimal solution
C_{1111}^S (N/mm)	1648
C_{1212}^S (N/mm)	3427
τ_{11}^0 (N/mm)	25.5

Conclusions

- An inverse approach is proposed to determine the interface parameters for composite bonded single-lap adhesively bonded joint.
- By utilizing the interface elasticity theory, it is possible to describe the interfacial strain distribution well and character the mechanics properties of an adhesively bonded interface.